

AUGMENTED REALITY IN ARCHITECTURAL CONSERVATION: A LITERATURE REVIEW ON CULTURAL HERITAGE PRESERVATION

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Abstract

With the development of Augmented Reality (AR) technology, the products developed in this field have become widespread. Today, AR technologies, which are used in many fields such as education, health, and tourism, are also widely used in architecture. It is aimed to research the studies on the use of AR technology for the conservation of architecture and cultural heritage, to reach academic publications and to obtain information about the subject. Cultural heritage sites are the common heritage of humanity in terms of historical, aesthetic, and artistic values. This heritage is being damaged by the developing city and vandalism and is even in danger of extinction. It is impossible to protect cultural heritage and transfer it to future generations with current technologies and conservation methods. AR technology can help preserve cultural heritage and pass it on to future generations.

This study identifies relevant research in AR, architecture, and cultural heritage. It aims to evaluate technology's development process from the past to the present. In the study, the articles in the field of AR are listed in two different databases (ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore). In which these research were carried out, the place and importance of architecture in these areas were analyzed. Since the study proceeded in a systematic order, the subject was narrowed, and 14 articles in the cultural heritage field were examined in detail. Applications and equipment used in academic studies on cultural heritage are added as a table. Our opinions on using applications and equipment developed for AR to protect cultural heritage are presented in the conclusion section.

Keywords: Augmented Reality, Architecture, Cultural Heritage, Architectural Conservation, Literature Research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Augmented Reality is the image created by adding virtual or digital objects to the real world (Azuma, 1997). AR produces applications that support professional practices that facilitate daily life and allow the practice in many branches of science (Milgram, Kishino, Takemura, & Utsumi, 1994). With hardware and software technologies that enable the user to perceive the environment, environmental data and interaction become digitally processed (Azuma, Baillot, Behringer, & Feiner, 2001). Thanks to this technology, digital or computer-generated pictures, audio, video, etc., data is simultaneously added on top of the real environment added (Coşkun, 2017). AR, which appeals to all five senses, is widely used in visual information transfer (Kippler & Rampolla, 2013).

When we look at the historical development of AR, it is seen that the most primitive examples are large-sized simulators (Caro, 1988). Later, with the emergence of graphical interfaces, head-mounted devices, and portable computers, the first AR studies were made close to what is known today (Caudell & Mizell, 1992). In addition to the developments in hardware, lots of software has also been developed, so AR technology has begun to be used in many areas.

With the developments in the field of software and hardware, architectural applications have emerged. Today, applications such as Morpholio AR Sketchwalk, Ar Measure, and Fologram are used for visualization, measurement, or presentation in architecture. In the future, AR technology will be used more widely in architectural education, design, and visualization processes (Hajirasouli & Banihashemi, 2022).

Complex digital technologies such as simulations, computational design applications and immersive technologies are used for different purposes, such as reducing cost, shortening time, improving the design, and increasing overall project efficiency (Askaripoor, Farzaneh, & Knoll, 2022). To carry out architectural studies with AR, it is necessary to determine the visualization software and hardware developed by this technology. For this reason, it is aimed to research the existing software and hardware.

It is seen that AR is a useful tool for cultural heritage conservation, and technological developments in this field are progressing rapidly. In the future, it is anticipated that users will be able to access interactive and detailed information about the architectural and cultural heritage with AR applications and hardware specially developed for AR.

According to the research questions, this study investigated AR's development and usage areas. AR applications and equipment used to protect cultural heritage have been examined. According to the data obtained from the studies on augmented reality and cultural heritage in the literature, the positive and negative aspects of using AR in the conservation process were determined.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study aims to survey the studies on AR in the literature to identify, evaluate and understand related research in the field of AR and cultural heritage. Studies published in the IEEE Xplore and ScienceDirect databases in AR and Cultural Heritage have been extensively researched. The subject has been systematically narrowed by focusing on the research area. By evaluating the studies examined, it was determined which studies would be included in the compilation. The studies' results were synthesized in the review, and the conclusion section was formed. The steps followed in each stage of the research are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. The methodology was created, as seen in the figure above.

Two scientific databases were scanned with the keywords determined at the beginning of the research. The relevance of the publications obtained from the scanning was evaluated in terms of content, and those not related to the research field were eliminated. Analyses were created from the received data. As a result of a detailed examination of the publications, publications related to the subject were selected. Then, the

strengths and weaknesses of the use of AR in the field of cultural heritage were shared with the findings obtained from the reviewed articles.

2.1 Research Questions

Since this study is a systematic review, the research questions focus on determining the use of AR in cultural heritage and showing future possibilities.

Q.01: What is the usage rate of Augmented Reality technology in the field of Architecture within the industry?

Q.02: Which applications and equipment are used in Augmented Reality studies to protect cultural heritage?

Q.03: According to the data obtained from the studies on cultural heritage conservation, what are the potentials and limits of using Augmented Reality?

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The data extraction process involved five stages:

Initially, primary research was conducted to trace the evolution of AR over the years, with no inclusion or exclusion criteria applied at this stage. Academic studies were arranged chronologically, and development trends were graphically represented based on the years.

Subsequently, each article was meticulously assessed by examining its title, abstract, and keywords to address the research questions and gather data pertaining to the use of AR in architecture.

To collect data relevant to the intersection of AR and architecture, the titles, abstracts, and keywords of each article were reviewed and categorized based on their content. Academic publications pertinent to the field of architecture were selected and cataloged.

Publications related to cultural heritage were identified and listed by scrutinizing the summaries and conclusions of articles within the architecture domain.

Finally, articles contributing positively to research on cultural heritage conservation were subjected to full-text analysis.

Table 1 The process followed in the research.

RESEARCH PROCESS	DATA EXAMINED
General Research	Title, Authors, Publication year, Journal or Conference name
Research Questions	The order of viewing the research questions (Q.01, A.S.02, A.S.03)
Inclusion criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online availability. • Posts related to Augmented Reality.
Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadcasts unrelated to Augmented Reality. • Publications that examine outside the research topic. • Publications whose content is inaccessible. • Publications published in languages other than English.
Researched Answers in the Content of Academic Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Augmented Reality Use. • Usage Areas of Augmented Reality. • Using Augmented Reality in the field of cultural heritage. • Augmented Reality hardware and software. • Potentials and limits of Augmented Reality.

2.3 Data Collection

The research was conducted using keywords encompassing the entire study scope. The objective was to identify all relevant articles on the subject. Subsequently, the investigation was narrowed down to address the research questions. Keywords were selected as "Augmented Reality, Architecture, and Cultural Heritage." The following steps were undertaken during the search process:

- Determination of keywords.
- Verification of keywords in related articles.
- Selection of articles relevant to the subject while excluding those with similar wording and meaning.
- Refinement of the research topic by expanding the keywords.

2.4 Limitations

Given that this study adopted a systematic review approach, a screening process based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria was implemented. The selection criteria were defined, and the article selection process was carried out iteratively. Articles not focused on cultural heritage were excluded to facilitate a detailed examination of studies in this domain. Rigorous scrutiny was applied to determine the relevance of academic studies to the subject matter based on their titles, abstracts, keywords, and results. Each article was thoroughly reviewed to extract data related to AR and cultural heritage. Finally, all article contents were examined, and those deemed to contribute positively to the research were selected. Findings were evaluated, conclusions were drawn, and the conclusion section was formulated.

2.5 Selection Quality

A meticulous evaluation process was conducted to ensure the compatibility of selected studies with each other. The detailed research progress, methodology employed, and other selection parameters used in the study are reflected in the number of articles obtained.

The process unfolded as follows:

- Identification of academic studies on AR through literature search using keywords.
- Examination of literature-based studies according to AR usage areas to obtain data relevant to architecture.
- In-depth examination of academic studies in architecture, leading to the selection of publications on cultural heritage.
- Detailed scrutiny of academic studies on cultural heritage.
- Search for answers to the research questions within the examined academic studies.

2.6 Research Process

Between 2000 and 2021, a total of 8,243 academic studies matching the keyword "Augmented Reality" were identified in the IEEE Xplore and ScienceDirect databases. The study was then iterated cyclically to observe the number of studies across various usage areas classified under AR. A total of 1,263 studies were identified in diverse fields such as education, health, and architecture where AR is employed. These publications were visualized based on their usage areas. Subsequently, 226 academic publications related to the keywords "Augmented Reality" and "Architecture" were identified. Reviewing the contents of articles eliminated academic publications falling outside the research scope. A detailed review of 41 articles related to architecture was conducted. Additionally, 14 articles containing the keywords "Augmented Reality," "Architecture," and "Cultural Heritage" were thoroughly analyzed through full-text examination. Furthermore, a graphical representation characterizing the research progress was generated, as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Research's progress histogram.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Development of Augmented Reality in Architecture

Interest in AR technology has increased since the early 2000s. Particularly after 2000, there has been a rapid increase in academic studies. A total of 8243 academic publications were found in the ScienceDirect and IEEE Xplore databases, indicating that AR has become a popular research area in recent years.

3.2 Academic Studies in Augmented Reality and Architecture

A total of 226 academic publications were examined, with a focus on 41 publications related to architecture. This review has provided a deeper understanding of the relationship between AR and architecture.

3.3 Academic Publications on Cultural Heritage

A total of 14 articles have focused on cultural heritage. These articles examine the potentials and limitations of AR in the preservation, promotion, and interactive sharing of cultural heritage information.

3.4 Article Reviews

The selected articles delve into the relationship between AR and cultural heritage from various perspectives. Each article addresses the impact of AR technology on the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage in different ways.

3.5 Applications and Hardware Used in Augmented Reality Studies

The reviewed articles have focused on AR applications and cultural heritage. Each article systematically examines the use of different hardware and applications in detail.

3.6 Potentials and Limits of Using Augmented Reality

AR technology has significant potentials for the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage. However, there are also limitations such as hardware requirements and lighting conditions.

These results indicate that AR technology could play a significant role in the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage, and further research in this area is warranted in the future.

4. DISCUSSION

The results presented in the previous section shed light on the current state and trends of augmented reality (AR) research, particularly in the field of architecture and cultural heritage. These findings provide valuable insights into the development, applications, and implications of AR technology in academic studies.

4.1 Augmented Reality in Architecture: Trends and Implications

- The significant increase in academic publications related to AR in architecture since the early 2000s indicates a growing interest and recognition of AR technology in this field. This trend suggests that AR has become an essential tool for architects and designers, offering new possibilities for design, visualization, and presentation.
- The concentration of AR studies in certain areas, such as cultural heritage and urban design, highlights the potential of AR technology to address specific challenges and opportunities within the architectural domain. By focusing on these niche areas, researchers can explore innovative applications of AR that cater to the unique needs of architects, urban planners, and cultural heritage professionals.
- The analysis of AR usage areas reveals a diverse range of applications, including education, tourism, and advertising. This diversity reflects the versatility of AR technology and its ability to transcend traditional boundaries, enabling interdisciplinary collaborations and creative problem-solving approaches.
- Despite the increasing popularity of AR in architecture, several challenges and limitations persist, such as hardware requirements, processing speed, and lighting conditions. Addressing these challenges will be crucial for the widespread adoption and effective implementation of AR technology in architectural practice.

4.2 Cultural Heritage Preservation and Promotion Through AR

- The examination of academic publications related to cultural heritage underscores the significant role of AR technology in preserving, promoting, and experiencing cultural heritage sites and artifacts. AR offers unique opportunities to engage audiences, enhance learning experiences, and provide immersive storytelling environments.
- The reviewed articles demonstrate the diverse applications of AR in cultural heritage, including virtual reconstructions, interactive exhibits, and outdoor exploration tools. These applications leverage AR technology to bridge the gap between the physical and digital worlds, offering users new perspectives and insights into historical and cultural contexts.
- While AR holds great promise for cultural heritage preservation, challenges such as accessibility, accuracy, and sustainability must be addressed to ensure the long-term viability of AR-based initiatives. Collaborative efforts between researchers, cultural institutions, and technology developers will be essential for overcoming these challenges and maximizing the potential of AR in cultural heritage conservation.

4.3 Future Directions and Research Opportunities

- The findings presented in this study underscore the need for further research and innovation in the field of AR, particularly in architecture and cultural heritage. Future studies should focus on addressing the existing limitations of AR technology, exploring new applications and methodologies, and evaluating the effectiveness and impact of AR-based interventions.
- Interdisciplinary collaborations between architects, archaeologists, computer scientists, and cultural heritage experts will be critical for advancing the field of AR and unlocking its full potential in architectural design, preservation, and education.
- Additionally, efforts to enhance public awareness, accessibility, and inclusivity of AR applications in cultural heritage should be prioritized, ensuring that these technologies benefit diverse audiences and contribute to the democratization of heritage knowledge and experiences.

Overall, the results and discussions presented in this study provide valuable insights into the current state and future prospects of AR technology in architecture and cultural heritage. By addressing key challenges and opportunities, researchers and practitioners can harness the power of AR to transform the way we design, experience, and interact with the built environment and cultural heritage sites.

5. CONCLUSION

Augmented Reality seems to be a promising technology for preserving cultural heritage and transferring it to future generations. AR technology has the potential to protect and promote cultural heritage and interactive information sharing with its visual and interactive features. In this study, although the use of AR technology in the field of Architecture is 3.24% when the graphs showing the number of academic studies are examined, it is clear that AR will be used more actively in the coming period. As a result of the research, it has been seen that AR is an interactive data-sharing tool that can be used to protect cultural heritage and transfer it to future generations. Virtual copies of the cultural heritage created with AR can be presented to users digitally and interactively through developed applications. In smart devices where AR applications are used extensively, the environment must be detected through sensors such as GPS, Compass and Gyroscope. With special hardware, such as immersive architectures and wearable systems, the user can easily use AR technology interactively. AR content designed with Unity3d, Unreal Engine, and Vuforia software are presented with different hardware.

In this way, it will be possible to create historical and cultural awareness in users. Data belonging to cultural heritage has been damaged due to physical and environmental reasons and is in danger of extinction. With the created AR applications, interactive content that can be transferred for generations can be created. Therefore, AR can be used as an auxiliary tool for architectural preservation. AR technology is developing, and users' technology and hardware knowledge have yet to reach a sufficient level. For this reason, the fact that AR technology is open to problems can be described as its negative aspects.

As a result, it is predicted that AR technology will be a more useful tool for conserving cultural heritage; technology is developing in this field, and users will be able to access interactive and detailed information about cultural heritage with AR applications in the future.

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